

**A STUDY ON SOCIAL CONDITIONS OF ADIDRAVIDAS WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO VELLORE DISTRICT**

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Abstract

The Asidravidas were forced to undertake the jobs of scavenging hide and skin works, digging the grave yards, carrying the dead animals etc., They toiled from the dawn to sunset during the hot sun in the field of the landlords and filling their galleries. Even their huts were not owned by them and they were built at the corners of the paddy fields of their landlords. Thus, poverty drove them to the extent of pledging themselves to the landlords for sum of rupees between forty to fifty, mostly borrowed to meet their funeral expenses or marriages etc., Thus, the communal atrocities on Adi-Dravidas were the continuous process and unabated in Vellore District. Not even a day has been passing without an event of communal atrocity on Adi-Dravidas in Tamil Nadu, but all of them became un-noticed and not even a single offender was punished under the "Prevention of Civil Rights Act of 1955. Social Emancipation of Adi-Dravidas can be achieved by educating them and by taking effort to improve their economic conditions. Each Adi-Dravida to get equal status with others in the society.

Introduction

The Depressed Class was regarded as polluting the people of the higher castes permitted an individual was required to hold his hand in front of his mouth so as to prevent pollution by his breath. Members of the Depressed Classes did not have

access to public wells, tanks, and roads. They were denied entry into temples. They could not seek admission to certain schools and colleges nor by the assistance of the state. Admission was denied into Government Post Office, Courts and Choultries to these unfortunate people such places were meant for the poor and the needy. It was located at a considerable distance from the habitations of upper class Hindus. The slums of the Depressed did not have even the basic facilities and civic amenities.

Most of the members of the Depressed Classes were agricultural labourers, some of them were forced to undertake the jobs of scavenging hide and skin works, digging the grave yards, carrying the dead animals etc., They toiled from the dawn to sunset during the hot sun in the field of the landlords and filling their galleries. Even their huts were not owned by them and they were built at the corners of the paddy fields of their landlords. Thus, poverty drove them to the extent of pledging themselves to the landlords for sum of rupees between forty to fifty, mostly borrowed to meet their funeral expenses.

Each member of the Depressed Classes who worked as an agricultural labourer, received daily wage at the rate of two ordinary measures of paddy which worked out to one Madras measure. This too was not given to them at the end of their day's toil. Several members of the Depressed Classes served the landlords as bonded labourers. Such families were assigned twenty five cents of land for their own cultivation. The produce from this land and their daily worked out to about forty-two Madras measures of paddy per annum. How could a family subsist on the Consequently, the Depressed Classes could never pacify the pangs of hunger. There was also no relaxation in the quantum of labour extracted from them. The landlords were so they could always devise ways and means to delay or avoid payment. The Depressed Classes could never expect human treatment from their masters. It was quite common for the women of the Depressed Classes, even in an advanced stage of

pregnancy, to toil in the sweating heat. They could not even nurse their infants without being subjected to the wrath of the land lords. Both men and women had to work from sunrise to sunset.

Civil disabilities

The use of public wells, tanks and roads was prohibited to them. They had to draw drinking water from stinking muddy pools. Unkept hair, rags for clothing, diseased and weathered bodies, this was the general appearance of the Depressed Classes. They were not permitted to apply oil or comb their hair. The village barber's services were denied to them. They were required to dress themselves only in rags. They were prohibited from naming their children with names commonly used by the higher casts. They were forbidden to take up any profession or occupation other than scavenging and other menial tasks. These general conditions of Adi-Dravidas in Tamil Nadu are the common features with the Adi-Dravidas of Vellore District.

The communal atrocities as they were found in the Southern districts of Tamil Nadu. The womenfolk of the Depressed Classes never forced not to wear the upper garments and asked to dance nakedly during the festival times the male members of the Depressed Classes were not forced to wear their dothis up to their knees and to remove their chapples and as in the case of their brothers in the Southern district.

Removal of disabilities

The Depressed Classes have been denied their civic and civil rights for centuries. They were prohibited from entering public streets, highways, public buildings, public places, offices, hospitals courts. wells, tanks, fountains, hotels or restaurants, temples etc., and were treated as sub-human beings. In short they were called Hindus but they were not in the Hindu society. Even in the jails and hospitals

the Depressed Classes were segregated and meted out with ill treatment. In the jails, Depressed Class convicts were forced to carry the night soil and urine of the caste Hindu convicts. The rule number 464 of the jail Manual insisted the Depressed Class convicts in the jails, should discharge this filthy job. In the General Hospital also there was a special ward for the Depressed Class patients.

The prevented not only to use the civil rights but also they were forced to do such menial works. Until the Vellore Christian Medical Hospital was instituted the Adi-Dravida patients in the Government hospital were placed in separate ward and forced to do such a menial works. But the Christian Missionaries in their hospital treated them equally and never discriminated the patients on the basis of caste or colour. In course of time the rule number 464 of the jail manual was repealed and in the Vellore Central Jail and Adi-Dravidas convicts were treated on par with that of other convicts. During festival seasons in the Renukambal Temple at Padaivedu the Untouchables were not allowed to enter into the temple tank, and to participate in the festival events. The drinking water was supplied to them through a bamboo trunk. At the one end the caste Hindu water supplier used to pour the water and at the other end the thirsty Untouchable used to take the water by wide opening his mouth. So as to prevent the pollution, the distance from the host to the guest should be twenty feet was the traditional rule of the caste Hindus.

During the weekly markets in various places of North Arcot district the Adi-Dravidas ought to operate their business at the corner of the market or outside the market complex. In the case of purchasing vegetables the Untouchables were allowed to do their business only after the closing of the business hour. Therefore, they could not sell their goods and gain as in the case of others and purchase them as fresh as in the case of others. The famous weekly cattle markets are in Poigai, Pennathur, Onnupuram, Thiruvannamalai, Chengam, Ranipet and other places. Even in the case

of cattle markets the Adi-Dravidas were not allowed to be employed as brokers or selling and buying agents. They were also not allowed to sell their vegetables and other products in the public markets. And their goods were purchased by the caste Hindu agents at the lowest rate as they fixed.

The poor Adi-Dravidar to sell their cattles and fowls in the cattle fair to meet their upenses, but they were not allowed to get into the fair and sell them directly. They are purchased by some mediators and brokers who are all caste Hindus at their lowest quotations. In the case of purchasing bullocks, sheeps cocks, hens etc., also they ought to purchase them only through the agents or brokers of high castes at the rate of their own choice. On both the cases they were not allowed to deal directly either with the purchaser with the seller. Thus, the Adi-Dravidas were mutilated in their economic growth by the sin of Untouchability.

Civil Rights

The Depressed Classes were posted for bandobust duty during the Kalpathi temple festival in Malabar". It is to be usually, the car procession used to take place noted that out side the temple complex. The fact that the Depressed Classes were not permitted to view the festival even from out side the temple complex, shows the magnitude of segregation. In the Fourth Session of the Second Legislative Council 1926, R.Veerian questioned 'Whether the delay in burying the dead body of an Adi-Dravida in Ellasamanoor Village in Vellore taluk was due to the order of the Health Inspector and the opposition of the caste people of the locality to the use by the Adi-Dravidas of their customary burial ground and the public pathway leading to there. It was also alleged by R.Veerian that the Depressed Classes living in Kadapery in Walaja Taluk Vellore District were not to pass through the patta land of caste people while carrying dead bodies to their burial ground.

It was also pointed out by him that the Depressed Classes in this area were suffering for want of a well. It was alleged in the Legislative Council that riotings were caused by caste Hindus in the Thirumalpur Adi-Dravidar Cheri in Walaja Taluk. It was also alleged that the caste Hindus destroyed an Elementary School established by the Missionaries for the Depressed Classes. In Nemili Arakkonam Taluk Vellore District five matric and one P.U.C. students belonging to Adi-Dravida community went to witness a village drama on 19.10.68 arranged by caste Hindus. They were asked by the- caste Hindus to sit at a separate place. When they refused to do so, students were attacked and one boy was iniured". In Konalam of Gudiyatham taluk. Vellore District. The communal trouble between Adi-Dravidas and Reddiyas community. In September 1982 a Harijan woman was died and her body was carried to the burial ground through the lands of caste Hindus. The original burial ground of the Adi-Dravidas was encroached by the caste Hindus land lords and hence the Government allotted a new burial ground to them. Since the Government supported the Adi-Dravidas and caused for getting their new burial ground the caste Hindu land lords wanted to take revenge against Adi-Dravidas.

They abducted an 'Adi-Dravida women named Mallika with her three children and four caste Hindus raped the women. Murugesan the husband of Mallika filed the case in the police station, but the police refused to file it. The caste Hindus ofthe Konalam village as a whole joined together and threatened the Adi-Dravidas abode and driven out them. Helpless Adi-Dravidas ran away from the village and scattered here and there. Even though the case was proved by the medical report that Mallika was raped by four persons, the social justice was not awarded to the Adi-Dravidas". Usually the frequent communal clashes were occurred at the events of village festivals, Say for example in 1976, in Karai village, there was an annual festival of Goddess Ponniamman. The celestial marriage ceremony of one-man was celebrated for a week in which the Adi-Dravida bridegroom ised to tie Thali around

the reek of Ponniamman. He used to feed with rich food by the caste Hindus house holders. The expenses incurred for the festivals was shared by both the caste Hindus and the Adi-Dravidas. But the caste Hindus refused to send the deity during the car festival to the Adi-Dravidas' abodes. The Adi-Dravidas demanded the procession should be extended upto their streets. But the caste Hindus bluntly refused to do so. Hence the enmity between the caste Hindus and the Adi-Dravida was strengthened. Even after the intervention of the Government and authorities of Hindu Religious Endowments Board the caste Hindus never moved an inch from their caste animosity. Even today the problem is remained as unsolved one in Karai village.

Thus, the communal atrocities on Adi-Dravidas were the continuous process and unabated in Vellore District. Not even a day has been passing without an event of communal atrocity on Adi-Dravidas in Tamil Nadu, but all of them became un-noticed and not even a single offender was punished under the "Prevention of Civil Right a Act of 1955. The researcher during his field survey recorded the oral evidences of the elders that acknowledged by the News Paper Reports. Some of the recent incidents of the district are recorded.

Legislative Measures to to Untouchables

The Colonial Government had left untouched the Civil Rights of Untouchables. Caste and Untouchability are the two great evils in the Indian Society. But the British took no steps either to deteriorate their aggressive powers or to determine their death. But the British who ruled over 200 years has completely ignored the evils of caste and Untouchability. Hence, B.R.Ambedkar openly called British as "Traitor and Betrayers of the Depressed Classes" in the Round Table Conference. The Untouchables were denied education and civil and civic amenities. Ambedkar said in the Round Table Conference". The Depressed Class man is a citizen but the Government not given him the rights of a citizen. He paid taxes out of which the

'schools were maintained but his children could not be admitted in to those schools'. He paid taxes out of which the wells were built but he has no right to take water from them; he paid taxes out of which roads were built but he has no right to use them. He paid taxes to up keep the State, but he himself was not entitled to hold offices in the State. He paid taxes to pay for education of the touchables; but the Untouchables were denied the right to education.

Really, the Untouchables were poor but they were not exempted from paying tax. They were treated as subjects but not as citizen! Citizens are entitled with all the Fundamental and Human Rights whereas the Untouchables were not entitled with the Fundamental or Human Right.

In Vellore District every year, from 24th to 30th January, District Adi-Dravidar Welfare Department celebrated Untouchability abolition week. State Adi-Dravidar Welfare Committee headed by the Justice Swamydurai submitted the memorandum for change of the name Untouchability Abolition Week Celebration into Manitbaneya, State Government accepted it, and issued order to the Adi-Dravidar and Tribe Welfare Department With a view to elevate the social status of Adi-Dravida on par with high caste, the Government of Tamil Nadu made effort to appoint Adi-Dravidas as Archakas with sufficient training to serve in Temples in Tamil Nadu from 1974 onwards. An initial success was made in this regards and 62 Adi-Dravidas were appointed as Archakas in the different temples of Tamil Nadu. In Vellore district unfortunately no data could be found for appointment of Adi-Dravidas Archakar.

Payment of Funeral Rite

The scheme for the grant of financial assistance to the Adi-Dravidas and converted Christian to meet expenditure in connection with funeral rites on the death of a member of a family at Rs.50 for each death, taking in to account the poor

economic conditions. This scheme was introduced in Vellore since 1970. From 1970 to 1986 the rate at Rs.50 was granted. The grant has been raised to Rs.100 from 1986 onwards. The poor Adi-Dravidas made use of this benefit through the inspector of Municipalities, Vellore.

Conclusion

The Removal of Civil Disabilities Act of 1938 and "The protection of Civil Rights Act of 1955 and its Amendment Act of 1972 were considered to be the corner stones of the Civil Rights of the Depressed Classes. More over the 'Republican Constitution of India' abolished the Untouchability under Article 17 and further assured the Depressed classes the full fledged liberty under the "Fundamental Rights. In order to materialise these phenomena, the Government of Tamil Nadu had executed in the form of Social Emancipation Programmes such as Awarding Gold medals for the couples of intercaste marriages; establishment of Community Centre to facilitate all the centers for mingling with each others Communities etc.

According to the declaration of Constitution of India and also social reformers, policy makers and general public, the social emancipation of Adi-Dravidas lay in the abolition of Untouchability, in giving all civic rights to them and proper education. The Untouchability Act 1955 has been amended and is known as the protection of Civil Rights Act and it came into force from 19 November 1976. Various provisions of this Act is also enforced strictly in Vellore District by a separate Police Officer in the rank of Deputy Inspector General of Police. In Vellore District 58 villages have been declared as Untouchability prone villages. Special attention was given to these villages requesting the District Collector to provide all amenities. Vellore does not come under the atrocity prone District of Tamil Nadu. Most of the cases registered under the PCR Act ended as acquitted or compounded, and the suffering victims were not properly attended to. In Vellore district the social

discrimination of Adi-Dravidas still exists. The truth is that the police department is scared of taking action against the accused who happen to be a non Adi-Dravida. Mostly the Communal clashes and conflicts and riots are compromised by the member of Legislative assembly and a few prominent leaders in the villages. When the non Adi-Dravida ML.A's intervene in such sensitive matters the Adi-Dravida victims get a raw deal at their hands.

In Vellore district, five Community Halls and two Community Centres are functioning with Social Workers, which created a separate identity for Adi-Dravidan in their localities. The social workers serve as an integral part of family welfare and children's progress in this district. Even though these buildings are used by the Adi-Dravidars in their localities. The social workers serve as an integral part of family welfare and children's progress in this district. Even though these buildings are used by the Adi-Dravidars to conduct their social festivals and marriages, this system might create wide gap between Adi-Dravidars and the non-Adi-Dravidars. The Government's policy of creating oneness among the Adi-Dravidars and non-Adi-Dravidars is not possible in this way. But the Government encourages inter-caste and inter-dining in order to create a casteless to creedless Community in Vellore district and elsewhere in Tamil Nadu. According to Article 17 of India constitution of 1950 it is believed that the Untouchability will be completely eradicated in India. The Untouchability Act of 1955 passed in order to punish the Caste-Hindus, those who practice this evil directly or indirectly. Yet the celebration of Harijan week by the Government of Tamil Nadu makes us to realize that the Untouchability still in rural villages and the Government's efforts have become fruitless.

At the district level the Deputy Inspector General of Police is taking prompt action against the committed on Adi-Dravidas and to ensure the implementation of the Government policy on the backward sections of society. Social

Emancipation of Adi-Dravidas can be achieved by educating them and by taking effort to improve their economic conditions. Each Adi-Dravida to get equal status with others in the society. The day when they get equal social status in the society is a day to celebrate in the life of Adi-Dravidas.

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